

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Schouten.id to Increase Brand Awareness and Purchase Intention

Ilmi Fitri¹, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan²

^{1,2}Institute Technology Bandung

ABSTRACT: Schouten.id is a local men's fashion brand that sells basic wear products and was founded in 2017. Schouten currently has five product categories: outerwear, shirts, pants, and hats. Every year, the number of MSMEs in the fashion sector grows, resulting in the emergence of many new competitors; however, some old competitors have also become obstacles. According to Schouten's sales data from 2020 to 2022, sales have fluctuated. The author conducted preliminary interviews with fifteen random people, only two of whom were familiar with the Schouten brand. With these findings, it is possible to conclude that Schouten's use of social media and promotional methods is still not optimal, resulting in a lack of brand awareness. According to the fishbone diagram's description of the problem, the fluctuations that occur in Schouten are also influenced by product and place factors. The purpose of this research is to determine what factors cause sales fluctuations at Schouten, what factors influence purchase intention, and what marketing strategy suggestions are appropriate to increase brand awareness at Schouten. To achieve the research objectives, the authors will conduct external and internal analysis, resulting in TOWS as a solution. PEST analysis, Porter's Five Forces Analysis, competitor analysis, and customer analysis were used for external analysis. Customer analysis was conducted by distributing questionnaires at random to 200 respondents, including potential customers. SmartPLS 4 is then used to process the data using the PLS-SEM approach. Then, for internal analysis, VRIO analysis, marketing mix, and STP are used. The TOWS matrix produced 11 strategies, and as many as six of them were chosen to formulate new marketing strategy proposals, which Schouten could then implement based on the implementation plans that had been created.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Fashion, Marketing Strategy, Purchase Intention, TOWS Matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

In terms of the contribution of the creative economy to GDP, Indonesia is the third largest country in the world, trailing only the United States and South Korea [1]. Fashion is one of the main focus areas in this creative industry, as well as one of the largest contributors to GDP and exports. Fashion is a key component of the creative economy's industry sector. It contributes nearly 20% to the creative economy industry sector [2]. The fashion industry has been identified as one of the most vital industries, accounting for a significant portion of the global economy. The fashion industry has been identified as one of the most vital industries, accounting for a significant portion of the global economy. One of the important factors that contribute to the fashion industry's positioning is that the clothes a person wears are a statement of their social status and a status symbol. Clothing is a known and required necessity all over the world [3]. This fashion-related company is also an MSME that has grown year after year. The number of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in 2019 reached 65.47 million units, according to the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs [4]. Schouten is one of the MSMEs involved in online fashion. Schouten is a local men's fashion brand that debuted in 2017 with five product categories. Schouten's 32 product types include outerwear, shirts, t-shirts, pants, and hats. Schouten communicates via Instagram and markets its products through marketplaces such as Shopee, Tokopedia, and TikTok Shop. With a total of 626 posts, the number of Schouten followers has now reached 21,000 people. However, the general public is unfamiliar with Schouten. As a result, the purpose of this research is to identify the root causes of Schouten's problems in order to develop a marketing strategy to increase brand awareness, which can lead to increased sales

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To boost Schouten sales, we first need to understand the factors that influence product purchase intentions. This study will also look at six different variables. Content quality can be defined by consumer perceptions of the accuracy, completeness, relevance, and timeliness of brand-related information on the brand's social media pages [5]. Social media interactions fundamentally alter brand-

customer communication [6]. Brand and product awareness is important for assisting with product comparisons and can lead to future purchase intentions [7]. Consumer online engagement represents individuals' interaction and participation in the social media environment [8]. The theory of planned behavior's (TPB) component, perceived behavioral control (PBC), has been identified as a significant moderating variable in the intention-behavior relationship [9]. When consumers form brand ratings and preferences between the evaluation and purchase decision stages, purchase intention develops [10].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Mixed-methods studies can gain knowledge or insights that independent qualitative and quantitative studies cannot. [11]. In this study, the author conducted interviews with Rizaldi, the founder of Schouten, using a qualitative research method. This interview was conducted to learn more about Schouten's business as well as the situation and business issues that Schouten is dealing with. Furthermore, the preliminary interview is classified as a qualitative method in this study about the Schouten brand. A questionnaire was distributed using the quantitative method beginning on November 1, 2022, and ending on December 4, 2022. The author uses the PLS-SEM method to process data for consumer analysis. A questionnaire was distributed using the quantitative method, beginning November 1, 2022, and ending December 4, 2022. The author uses the PLS-SEM method to process data for consumer analysis. Furthermore, this study takes two perspectives, namely on the company's external and internal conditions. PEST analysis, Porter's Five Forces, competitor analysis, and consumer analysis are all used in external analysis. The internal analysis then employs VRIO, STP, and marketing mix. It generates a SWOT analysis based on internal and external analysis, which then becomes the TOWS matrix as a business solution.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 below shows that the conceptual framework can be used without variable reduction. Based on the PLS-SEM results obtained with SmartPLS 4, all variables produce valid and reliable results.

Figure 1. Conceptual Path Model

According to the significance analysis results, because the p value is less than the 0.05 significance level, content quality, brand interactivity, brand awareness, and perceived control have a significant effect on purchase intention. One variable, however, consumer online involvement, has a p value of 0.137 and is therefore not significant.

Table I. Significance Result

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention	0,454	0,458	0,077	5,902	0,000
Brand Interactivity -> Brand Awareness	0,604	0,605	0,062	9,733	0,000
Consumer Online Engagement -> Purchase Intention	0,138	0,134	0,093	1,488	0,137
Content Quality -> Brand Awareness	0,174	0,178	0,068	2,544	0,011
Perceived Control -> Purchase Intention	0,298	0,302	0,074	4,035	0,000

Based on the external and internal analysis that has been carried out, a SWOT analysis is produced, which is then used to formulate the TOWS matrix.

Table II. TOWS Matrix

	Strength	Weakness
	S1. Design of Limited Products S2. Competitive Price	W1. Common product quality W2. Lack of product innovation W3. Lack of employee experience W4. The use of social media is not optimal W5. Providing the same customer relationship services as competitors
Opportunity	S-O Strategies	W-O Strategies
O1. There is a Government Policy in the Creative Industry Sector O2. Indonesia's Economic Growth is Increasing O3. TikTok is Becoming Increasingly Popular O4. Trends Environmentalists are in High Demand O5. Technological Advancement (Ecommerce) O6. Technological Advancement (3D body scanner)	SO1. Making special-edition products for environmentalists (S1, O2, O3, O4, O5)	WO1. Create products for women only (W2, O2, O3, O5) WO2. Producing extra items such as bags, wallets, accessories, socks, and belts (W2, O2, O3, O5) WO3. Create video content with a variety of themes (W4, O3)
Threat	S-T Strategies	W-T Strategies
T1. Threat of New Entrants T2. Rivalry Among Existing Competitors	ST1. Influencers are being used to promote Schouten's limited product designs (S1, T1, T2) ST2. Participating in marketing events such as exhibitions or business talk to raise brand awareness for Schouten (S1, T1, T2)	WT1. Create products for women only (W2, T1, T2) WT2. Producing extra items such as bags, wallets, accessories, socks, and belts (W2, T1, T2) WT3. Create video or post Instagram story content with a variety of themes (W4, T1, T2) WT4. Improving the quality of human resources by taking courses on entrepreneurship and implementing rewards (W3, T1, T2) WT5. Improving Customer Relationship Management Services (W4, T1, T2)

Based on the TOWS matrix table above, the results show a number of strategies that are thought to be appropriate for use in Schouten and are analyzed based on their external and internal conditions. However, because not all strategies apply to Schouten, the best strategy is chosen to create a new marketing strategy.

5. CONCLUSION

Schouten, on the other hand, uses social media ineffectively, as evidenced by a 0.33% engagement rate on Instagram. As a result of this study's proposal, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Several factors, such as promotions, products, and locations, have been shown to cause fluctuations in Schouten's sales when determining the causes of fluctuating Schouten sales. Ineffective marketing communication programs, limited product variations, common designs, limited budgets, and limited sales channels are some of the main causes of problems at Schouten.
2. Factors influencing purchase intention, namely brand awareness, have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention with a p value of 0.000. Perceived control has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention with a p value of 0.000.
3. Propose the best marketing strategy for Schouten to increase brand awareness by implementing the following strategies: making products for women only; producing additional items such as bags, wallets, accessories, socks, and belts; creating video content with various themes; using influencers to promote limited Schouten product design; improving the quality of human resources by taking entrepreneurship courses and implementing rewards; improving the quality of human resources by taking entrepreneurship courses and implementing rewards.

REFERENCES

1. I. F. Timorria, "Tiga Subsektor Ekonomi Kreatif Jadi Penyumbang Terbesar PDB," *Ekonomi*, Aug. 30, 2020. <https://ekonomi.bisnis.com/read/20200830/12/1284797/tiga-subsektor-ekonomi-kreatif-jadi-penyumbang-terbesar-pdb> (accessed Sep. 28, 2022).
2. R. P. Ananda, "Menparekraf Sandiaga Ungkap Industri Fashion Salah Satu Tulang Punggung Ekonomi Kreatif Indonesia," Nov. 30, 2021. <https://www.inews.id/travel/belanja/menparekraf-sandiaga-ungkap-industri-fashion-salah-satu-tulangpunggung-ekonomi-kreatif-indonesia> (accessed Sep. 29, 2022).
3. S. F. Yeo, C. L. Tan, A. Kumar, K. H. Tan, and J. K. Wong, "Investigating the impact of AI-powered technologies on Instagrammers' purchase decisions in digitalization era—A study of the fashion and apparel industry," *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change*, no. 177, pp. 1–14, Feb. 2022.
4. M. I. Mahdi, "Berapa Jumlah UMKM di Indonesia?," *DataIndonesia.id*, Jan. 19, 2022. <https://dataindonesia.id/sektorriil/detail/berapa-jumlah-umkm-di-indonesia> (accessed Sep. 30, 2022).
5. J. Carlson, M. Rahman, R. Voola, and N. De Vries, "Customer engagement behaviours in social media: capturing innovation opportunities," *J. Serv. Mark.*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 83–94, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1108/JSM-02-2017-0059.
6. A. M. Kaplan and M. Haenlein, "Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media," *Bus. Horiz.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 59–68, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003.
7. P. Foroudi, "Influence of brand signature, brand awareness, brand attitude, brand T reputation on hotel industry's brand performance," *Int. J. Hosp. Manag.*, no. 76, pp. 271–285, May 2018.
8. V. Barger, J. W. Peltier, and D. E. Schultz, "Social media and consumer engagement: a review and research agenda," *J. Res. Interact. Mark.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 268–287, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1108/JRIM-06-2016-0065.
9. I. Ajzen, "Perceived Behavioral Control, Self-Efficacy, Locus of Control, and the Theory of Planned Behavior¹," *J. Appl. Soc. Psychol.*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 665–683, Apr. 2002, doi: 10.1111/j.1559-1816.2002.tb00236.x.
10. Indrawati, P. C. Putri Yones, and S. Muthaiyah, "eWOM via the TikTok application and its influence on the purchase intention of somethinc products," *Asia Pac. Manag. Rev.*, p. S1029313222000392, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2022.07.007.
11. A. O'Cathain, E. Murphy, and J. Nicholl, "Integration and Publications as Indicators of 'Yield' From Mixed Methods Studies," *J. Mix. Methods Res.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 147–163, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1177/1558689806299094.

Cite this Article: Ilmi Fitri, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan (2023). Proposed Marketing Strategy for Schouten.id to Increase Brand Awareness and Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(1), 255-258